

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Mandelic Acid by Vanadium(V): Energy and Entropy of Activation

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Reactions between mandelic acid and vanadium(V) in 0.165, 0.26, and 0.63 M $[H_3O^+]$ in sulphuric acid at 25°, 30°, and 35° and 1.07 and 1.286 M $[H_3O^+]$ in perchloric acid at 20.6°, 25°, and 30° have been studied. The evaluated values of energy of activation, frequency factor, and entropy of activation are 14.0 ± 0.3 k cal., $4.7 \pm 1.0 \times 10^8$ litres mole sec. and -19.86 ± 0.3 e.u. respectively, in perchloric acid and sulphuric acid media. Effect of dielectric constant and that of vanadium (IV) and Cu(II) ions have been studied and discussed.

In a previous communication¹ the authors studied the kinetics of the oxidation of mandelic acid by quinquevalent vanadium in sulphuric acid and showed the reaction to be of first order. It was suggested there that the active oxidant might either be $V(OH)_5^{2+}$, $VO.OH^{2+}$, or a sulphato complex of vanadium(V) and the acid suffered oxidation through the free radical, $C_6H_5\dot{C}H(OH)$; to benzaldehyde, the rate-determining step being the decarboxylation of mandelic acid-vanadium (V) transition complex to provide free radical. It has been shown here that the active oxidant both in perchloric acid and sulphuric acid between the acidities used is $V(OH)_5^{2+}$, as suggested by Ramsey *et al.*² and Littler and Waters³.

EXPERIMENTAL

A standard solution of vanadium (V) in sulphuric acid and perchloric acid was prepared by suspending sodium metavanadate (A.R.) in distilled water and adding a known volume of standard sulphuric acid and perchloric acid (80% A.R.) respectively. A 0.1 N vanadium (V) solution in perchloric acid was thus obtained which did not precipitate V_2O_5 for a week. The acidity of the solutions was calculated using the equation

Acetic acid-water mixtures of 40 to 80% in acetic acid were prepared by adding requisite amounts of glacial acetic acid (A.R., 99.95%) to vanadium (V) solutions. Cu(II) salt solution was prepared in known concentration of H_2SO_4 . Ionic strength of the solutions was maintained constant at 1.6 by adding requisite amounts of potassium sulphate solutions.

Kinetic Measurements.—Known volumes of standard mandelic acid and vanadium (V) solutions in equivalent ratio (equivalent weight of mandelic acid being taken to be one

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1. *Curr. Sci.*, 1962, 31, 11.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1695.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4046.

half of its molecular weight) were kept in a thermostat for sufficient time to attain its temperature (variation $\pm 0.05^\circ$) and then mixed. The reaction mixture was quenched in iced phosphoric acid-sulphuric acid mixture and the unchanged oxidant was estimated by titrating it against a standard Mohr's salt solution, using diphenylbenzidine as an indicator. The second order rate constants were obtained from the slope of the plot of $1/(a-x)$ against 't'. The values were fairly constant till 60% completion of the reaction, beyond which the rate constants fell off the linear relationship. Initial rates were measured, using Mirror and Scale device⁴.

DISCUSSION

Oxidation of mandelic acid by vanadium(V) can be expressed as:

[Found: 1.9 equivalent of vanadium (V) per mole of mandelic acid¹].

The dependence of rate of H^+ -ion concentration in H_2SO_4 can be explained by considering the following equilibria:

Equilibrium of the type (1) will show a first order dependence of log of second order rate constant, k_2 , on H_+ , the relevant Hammett acidity function⁵ for the addition of a proton to a cation. Since the values of H_+ are not available and it has been shown by Bonner and Lockhart⁵ that H_0 and H_+ change in a parallel manner in certain ranges, a first order dependence should be observed between log k_2 and H_0 values. Table I shows the dependence of log k_2 on H_3O^+ and H_0 . The values of H_0 at different acidities have been obtained from the tables of Paul and Long⁶. A first order dependence of log k_2 on H_3O^+ in sulphuric acid is observed, whereas log k_2 does not seem to approximate the desired order on H_0 . The sulphato complex of the type $\text{V(OH)}_3\text{HSO}_4^+$ would mean a second order dependence on H_3O^+ , which has not been observed. This shows that the active oxidiser is V(OH)_3^{3+} .

TABLE I

Dependence of rate on $[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]$ and H_0 in H_2SO_4 .
 $[\text{Vanadium (V)}]=0.01 M$. $[\text{Mandelic acid}]=0.005 M$. Temp. = 33.0° .

$[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]$.	$k_2 \times 10^2$. (litres/mole sec.).	$-\text{H}_0$.	$k_2 \times 10^2/[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]$.	$2 + \log k_2/(-\text{H}_0)$.
0.750 M	2.99	0.070	3.98	6.79
0.814	3.26	0.110	4.00	4.68
0.899	3.56	0.180	3.85	3.06
0.963	3.92	0.225	4.07	2.83
1.069	4.17	0.300	3.90	2.07

4. Latashaw, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 793.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 364.

6. *Chem. Rev.*, 1957, 57, 1.

Addition of vanadyl (IV) ions has a slight but definite retarding effect on the reaction rate (Table II). This might probably be due to complex formation between vanadyl ions and mandelic acid molecules, thereby reducing the concentration of free mandelic acid molecules and hence the rate.

TABLE II

Dependence of rate on initial vanadyl ion conc. at 32.5°.

[V(V)] = 0.01M. [Mandelic acid] = 0.005M. [H₃O⁺] = 0.14M. μ = 1.6M

[Vanadium (IV)] (M)	..	0.0	0.0025	0.005	0.01
Initial rates $\times 10^8$ (moles/lit. sec.)	..	1.80	1.75	1.68	1.55

The reaction has been studied in various acetic acid-water binary mixtures. The rate increases with decrease in dielectric constant of the mixture, i.e., the decrease in mole fraction of water (Table III). The dielectric constants of acetic acid-water mixtures are not known. Solvent-solute interaction seems to be a more significant factor in influencing the rate, dielectric constant being secondary⁷ since the selective solvation and greater electrostatic attraction of the solute for the more polar component of a mixed solvent may produce near the solute particle a region of dielectric constant, different from average or bulk dielectric constant. A linear relation between mole fraction of water and reaction rate may then be expected as has already been found (Table III).

TABLE III

Dependence of rate on acetic acid-water composition.

[Vanadium (V)] = 0.01M. [Mandelic acid] = 0.005M. H₃O⁺ = 0.165M. Temp. = 20°.

% Acetic acid	..	40	50	60	70	80
*Mole fraction of water	..	0.8283	0.7630	0.6822	0.5801	0.4458
$k_2 \times 10^2$ (litres/mole sec.)	..	2.75	3.47	4.36	5.59	7.30

*Data have been taken from the table of Venkatasubramanian, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 541.

In 80% acetic acid and above, the yellow colour of vanadium (V) changed to reddish yellow and the rate was faster than that expected.

TABLE IV

Effect of temperature on reaction rate and other thermodynamic data in sulphuric acid and perchloric acid.

[Vanadium (V)] = 0.01M. [Mandelic acid] = 0.005M.

[H ⁺]	$k_2 \times 10^2$ (litres/mole. sec.) at				ΔE (k cal.)	$pZ \times 10^8$ (lit./mole sec.)	ΔS (e.u)
	20.6°.	25°.	30°.	35°.			
*0.165 M	..	1.42	2.10	3.10	14.1	4.0	-20.05
0.260	..	1.70	2.53	3.75	14.3	4.8	-19.89
0.630	..	2.01	2.95	4.37	14.1	5.6	-19.37
†1.070	1.82	2.60	3.99	..	13.9	3.7	-20.20
1.286	2.03	2.90	4.33	..	13.7	4.1	-20.01

*In sulphuric acid medium.

† In perchloric acid medium.

The reaction has been found to obey the Arrhenius equation between the temperature range studied both in sulphuric acid and perchloric acid. The values of thermodynamic constants calculated are listed in Table IV. The parallel line plots between $\log k_2$ and

7. Gelles *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2918.

$1/T$ in both media (Fig. 1) provide the value of energy of activation as 14.0 ± 0.3 k cal. The values of frequency factor and entropy of activation are also nearly the same in both the media (Table IV). This points to the similarity of the mechanism in these media, the nature of the reactants and the transition complex being the same.

FIG. 1. Variation of $\log k_2$ with $1/T$ in H_2SO_4 and perchloric acid.
[Vanadium (V)]=0.01M. [Mandelic acid]=0.005M.

1.	H_2O	1.070M	in perchloric acid.
2.	"	1.286	"
3.	"	0.165	" H_2SO_4
4.	"	0.280	"
5.	"	0.630	"

The increase in initial rates by addition of Cu(II) ions (Table V) suggests the initial reaction to be the decarboxylation of the transition complex formed between vanadium (V) and mandelic acid. These ions are known for their catalytic decarboxylating action in solution⁶. This is in conformity with the proposed rate-determining step by the authors.

TABLE V

Effect of initial Cu(II) ions on initial rates.

[Vanadium (V)]=0.01M. [Mandelic acid]=0.005M. $[H_3O^+]=0.6$ M.

[Cu(II)] (mole/litre)	..	..	0.00	0.03
Initial rates $\times 10^3$ (moles/lit.hr.)	..	..	6.60	15.96
$k_2 \times 10^2$ (lit./mole.sec.)	..	..	1.10	1.97

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